

Sharing Research Beyond Academia

A Guide to Free Repositories for Researchers

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Glossary

Term	Meaning
APO	The Analysis & Policy Observatory is a free, open access public policy repository in Australia which collects grey literature. ¹
CC	Creative Commons ²
CCAT	Centre for Culture and Technology
DOI	Digital Object Identifier ³ - a unique persistent identifier, with associated metadata also recorded about the research output.
ERA	Excellence in Research for Australia – a national framework for research evaluation in Australian universities. ⁴
FAIR	A set of guiding principles to make research Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ⁵
Figshare	Figshare is a repository owned by Digital Science, a company whose other products include Symplectic Elements and Dimensions. ⁶ The repository https://figshare.com/ is free, and Figshare also offers a paid customisable institutional repository product. ⁷
grey literature	‘Published and unpublished research, produced by government, academia, business and industry, that is not controlled by commercial publishers’ ⁸
Humanities Commons CORE	Humanities Commons is a non-profit network funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and Michigan State University. Their CORE repository was funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities’ Office of Digital Humanities. ⁹
identifier	An identifier is a label used to uniquely name something, for example a URL or an ISBN. A persistent identifier such as a DOI will always point to a research output over time, even if the research output moves around within a repository. ¹⁰
metadata	Information used to describe an item, which adds meaning and can make the item more findable ¹¹
NTROs	‘Non-traditional research outputs’ is a term used in the assessment of grey literature research outputs by ERA. These research outputs are works other than journal articles and monographs. Under ERA definitions, NTROs include research reports for public sector, industry, not for profit and others. ERA do not recognise

¹ <https://apo.org.au/page/about-apo>

² <https://creativecommons.org/>

³ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁴ <https://www.arc.gov.au/excellence-research-australia>

⁵ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

⁶ <https://www.digital-science.com/>

⁷ <https://knowledge.figshare.com/institutions>

⁸ <https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=863554&p=6191902>

⁹ <https://hcommons.org/about-humanities-commons/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ands.org.au/guides/persistent-identifiers-awareness>

¹¹ <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/describing-information/metadata>

	submissions to public inquiries, blogs or online articles as eligible for assessment. ¹²
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID, a free unique, persistent identifier for researchers ¹³
repository	A repository is an online space for researchers to create a record of their grey literature, and share a copy.
Zenodo	A research repository which is free for researchers from any discipline, and any country, to save their research outputs to. ¹⁴ Zenodo is funded by the European Commission, CERN and the Arcadia Fund. ¹⁵

¹² p39, <https://www.arc.gov.au/file/3781/download?token=Wq9o-CbM>

¹³ <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁵ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

1 Introduction

This guide is intended for researchers who produce want to share their research beyond academia in free repositories. This guide provides help on the following topics:

- How to get a DOI
- Repository options
- How to save research outputs to Zenodo
- How to save research outputs to Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE
- Examples and templates of metadata for your research outputs
- How to add research outputs to your ORCID record
- Tips for sharing your research outputs beyond academia

This guide is a project deliverable from a five-week project funded by the Centre for Culture and Technology (CCAT) at Curtin University.

What research outputs are covered in this guide?

Researchers disseminate the outputs of their research within academia in journal articles and books. Many researchers also share their research beyond academia with the wider community. Examples of these research outputs include reports, news articles and presentations, which are sometimes collectively termed as grey literature. Grey literature was defined at two grey literature conferences (Luxembourg in 1997 and New York City in 2004) as electronic and print information produced by academia, government, industry, and business, and not controlled by publishers (White et al., 2013, p. 3).

Well-known forms of grey literature are 'theses and dissertations, government documents, conference papers, white papers, blog and discussion posts, and press releases' (Mering, 2018, p. 238). Grey literature can also include maps, newsletters, factsheets and interviews, and provides a channel for researchers to share their findings and impact communities, industry and government (GreyNet International, 2014). Other forms of grey literature are posters, infographics, videos, podcasts and interview recordings. The scope of this guide is these types of research outputs, rather than journal articles and books. Throughout this guide the terms grey literature and research outputs will be used interchangeably.

What is digital preservation?¹⁶

Many researchers share outside academia via personal websites and institutional websites. However, sharing research outputs on websites makes them vulnerable, as they can disappear when these websites cease to be maintained or updated (for example when project funding comes to an end). Digital preservation is where repositories commit to storing and backing up your research outputs over long periods of time.

¹⁶ Quigley, Niamh, & Montgomery, Lucy. (2022). Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

What are repositories?¹⁷

Repositories provide an online space for researchers to save and share their research outputs. Repositories can be institutional, subject-based or general. Institutional repositories store the research data and outputs of researchers at that institution only, while subject-based repositories store research data and outputs relating to a specific research area. General repositories such as Zenodo store the research data and outputs of anyone. This guide covers three free general repositories – Zenodo, Figshare and Humanities Commons CORE.

Some institutional repositories are already collecting grey literature and sharing it as open access (Lawrence et al., 2015, p. 235; Tsunoda et al., 2017, p. 8). However, more effort is needed by libraries to preserve and curate grey literature (Lynch, 2017, p. 129), and formally include diverse grey literature in their collection policies (Marsolek et al., 2021, p. 59). Australia has a dedicated open access repository called the Analysis & Policy Observatory (<https://apo.org.au/>), which stores and shares research findings including grey literature.

What is metadata?

The information recorded about research outputs is known as metadata. For example, metadata about a report could include Title, Author(s), Year Published, Funder, Copyright information and a Contact email address. The more metadata you add, the easier it will be for others to find your research outputs. High quality metadata is key to ensuring that research outputs are **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable or FAIR¹⁸.

1.1 Why you should save your research outputs to a repository

Multiple benefits of storing research outputs in a repository exist for researchers:

- Grey literature that is stored in a repository is more visible to other researchers, industry, government and communities, with a potentially bigger impact (Kingsley, 2020, pp. 286–287; Simons & Richardson, 2013, p. 6)
- The use of a persistent identifier (for example a DOI) enables gathering of citation information about the grey literature. These persistent identifiers can also be used to track mentions via Altmetrics or Event Data (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Grey literature in repositories is digitally preserved and not vulnerable to disappearing from websites (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Authors have the ability to see statistics for grey literature views and downloads (Kingsley, 2020, p. 287)
- Credibility can be added to the research outputs by being stored in a university repository
- The research outputs can be updated if needed, and the DOI can point to the latest version
- Many repositories are indexed by Google, thus making research outputs more findable.

¹⁷ Quigley, Niamh, & Montgomery, Lucy. (2022). Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

¹⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

1.2 How to use this guide

Repository options

If you are trying to choose a repository, go to the following sections in this guide:

- [Section 3.1.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Zenodo](#)
- [Section 3.2.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Figshare](#)
- [Section 3.3.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Humanities Commons CORE](#)

How to get a DOI

Different ways of getting a DOI for your research outputs can be found in:

- [Section 2 Important metadata](#)

How to save to Zenodo

Detailed instructions are provided for Zenodo as it has the strongest digital preservation policy, and most flexible copyright options.

- [Section 4 How to save to Zenodo](#)

How to save to Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE

If you would like to try uploading your research outputs to Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE, go to the following sections:

- [Section 3.2.2 How to save to Figshare](#)
- [Section 3.3.2 How to save to Humanities Commons CORE](#)

Examples and templates of metadata

If you are looking for examples and templates of metadata text to add into your research outputs, go to:

- [Section 4.3.3 Metadata template](#)
- [Section 4.3.4 Metadata example](#)
- [Section 4.3.5 Metadata checklist](#)

How to add your research outputs to ORCID

To find out how to add your research outputs to your ORCID record, go to

- [Section 5 Adding Research Outputs to ORCID](#)

Tips on sharing beyond academia

To learn more about sharing your research outputs and alternative metrics, go to

- [Section 6 Sharing your research outputs beyond academia](#)

1.3 Useful links and contacts

Curtin University Library resources

Topic	Link
Non-traditional research outputs	https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=941541&p=6816645
Alternative metrics	https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=889921&p=6401380
Copyright	https://copyright.curtin.edu.au/
Applying Creative Commons licences	https://www.curtin.edu.au/copyright/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Applying-CC-Licenses.pdf
How to get a Curtin-generated DOI	https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=941541&p=6827384
Tips for maximising visibility and publishing impact	https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=941541&p=6819606

Useful contacts

Need help with...	Contact
Copyright	library-copyright@curtin.edu.au
Getting a Curtin-generated DOI	espace@curtin.edu.au

2 Important Metadata

Metadata is information used to describe an item, which adds meaning and can make the item more findable.¹⁹ Have you ever read grey literature that was missing helpful metadata such as the year it was written in, or how to contact the authors? Important metadata for grey literature includes:

- A unique identifier such as a DOI
- Title
- Authors, contributors and reviewers, and any acknowledgements
- Version
- Research group
- Date published
- How the grey literature can be reused – copyright/Creative Commons
- Suggested citation
- Funder
- Contact email (can be an individual or a group)

See [Section 4.3](#) in this guide for an example of metadata in a report, and a reusable template that you can copy and paste into your grey literature.

Curtin University Library has also written a helpful guide on applying Creative Commons licences within a report – see <https://www.curtin.edu.au/copyright/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Applying-CC-Licenses.pdf>

2.1 How to get a DOI

A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is a unique persistent identifier, with associated information about you and your grey literature also recorded. The information or metadata associated with DOIs is stored by DOI minting agencies (for example DataCite and CrossRef). Using DOIs makes your grey literature citable, and is widely used for different types of research outputs. DOI metadata including citation information can then be harvested and reused by other applications and systems, which increases the findability and visibility of your research outputs.

There are two options for getting a DOI to use for your research outputs:

- Get a DOI from Curtin University Library ([find out how to do this here](#))
- Get a DOI from a free repository such as Zenodo, Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE:
 - see [section 3](#) in this guide for Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE
 - see [section 4](#) for Zenodo.

¹⁹ <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/describing-information/metadata>

3 Repository Options

This section looks at three free repositories where you can share your research outputs – Zenodo, Figshare, and Humanities Commons CORE. The advantages and disadvantages of each repository relevant to grey literature is listed.²⁰

3.1 Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is hosted by CERN. CERN is an intergovernmental organization also known as the European Laboratory for Particle Physics, and is one of the world’s largest and most respected centres of scientific research. The CERN research repository, Zenodo, is free for researchers from any discipline, and any country, to use. The repository is funded by the European Commission, CERN and the Arcadia Fund.²¹

3.1.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Zenodo

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free for researchers • Provides a DOI • Can look up and link to funded grants • Can link to your ORCID • Broad licencing options • ORCID can import your Zenodo grey literature (via DataCite) • Can specify a community to add your grey literature to • Can see the number of views and downloads of your grey literature • Zenodo will store your grey literature for at least 20 years²² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None noted

3.1.2 How to save to Zenodo

See [section 4](#) in this guide for detailed instructions on how to save grey literature to Zenodo.

3.1.3 Communities in Zenodo

In Zenodo, communities can be set up to gather together a collection of research outputs. This functionality can be used in a number of ways, for example:

- As a way to gather together work by a single researcher. For example, Prof. Daniel O'Donnell has created a [collection called Daniel Paul O'Donnell Personal Repository](#)

²⁰ This section is derived from Quigley, Niamh, & Montgomery, Lucy. (2022). Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

²¹ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

²² Zenodo – 20 years at least (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)

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- As a way to gather together work by a group of researchers. For example, the [Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative \(COKI\) has a Zenodo community](#) including articles, conference papers and presentations by COKI researchers.
- As a way to gather together work relating to a specific project. The '[Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust](#)' [Zenodo community](#) contains outputs and documents related to the Andrew W Mellon Foundation funded research project *Developing a Pilot Data Trust for Open Access eBook Usage*.

3.1.4 More help on Zenodo

<https://help.zenodo.org/>

3.2 Figshare

<https://figshare.com/>

Figshare is owned by Digital Science, a company whose other products include Symplectic Elements and Dimensions.²³ The repository <https://figshare.com/> is free, and Figshare also offers a paid customisable institutional repository product.²⁴

3.2.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Figshare

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free for researchers • Provides a DOI • Can look up and link to funded grants • Can link to your ORCID • Can see the number of views, downloads and citations of your grey literature • ORCID can import your Figshare grey literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figshare can suspend this free service at any time²⁵ • Limited licencing options for free Figshare: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CC BY 4.0 – others can download your work, and remix it (even commercially) with attribution • CCO – no copyright, your work is in the public domain

3.2.2 How to save to Figshare

1. Create a Figshare account <https://figshare.com/account/register>
2. Follow the guide 'How to upload and publish your data' <https://help.figshare.com/article/how-to-upload-and-publish-your-data>
3. A suggested **Item type** for grey literature when uploading to Figshare is 'Online resource'

3.2.3 Collections in Figshare

Alternatively, you can create a collection in Figshare containing multiple files that you have already uploaded. See Figshare's guide for how to do this:

<https://help.figshare.com/article/how-to-use-collections>

3.2.4 More help on Figshare

Tutorials <https://help.figshare.com/section/tutorials>

User guides <https://help.figshare.com/section/user-guides>

²³ <https://www.digital-science.com/>

²⁴ <https://knowledge.figshare.com/institutions>

²⁵ Figshare 'reserves the right, at its sole discretion, to change, suspend, or discontinue any part of the Service at any time without notice to you.' (<https://figshare.com/terms>)

3.3 Humanities Commons CORE

<https://hcommons.org/core/>

Humanities Commons is a non-profit network funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and Michigan State University. Their CORE repository was funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities' Office of Digital Humanities.²⁶

3.3.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Humanities Commons CORE

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free for researchers • Provides a DOI • Can see the number of downloads of your grey literature • ORCID can import your Humanities Commons CORE grey literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humanities Commons can suspend this free service at any time²⁷ • Cannot look up funded grants • Does not add your ORCID to the metadata

3.3.2 How to save to Humanities Commons CORE

1. Create a Humanities Commons CORE account <https://hcommons.org/membership/>
2. Click on 'Share & preserve your work' to upload (or <https://hcommons.org/deposits/item/new/>)
3. Add the file for the grey literature by selecting 'Select File'
4. Select the **Item Type** depending on the type of grey literature:
 - Blog post
 - Interview
 - Magazine section
 - Newspaper article
 - Online publication
 - Podcast
 - Report
 - White paper
5. Fill in the Title, Description, Contributors, Subjects, Tags, File Type, Publication Type, Date of Creation, and Creative Commons License.

3.3.3 Groups in Humanities Commons CORE

Humanities Commons offers groups, where researchers with similar interests can share an online space. This includes the ability to share grey literature in Humanities Commons CORE with a group. See the Humanities Commons guide on groups for more details: <https://support.hcommons.org/guides/groups/>

²⁶ <https://hcommons.org/about-humanities-commons/>

²⁷ Michigan State University 'reserves the right to modify, suspend, or discontinue the network, with or without notice, at any time' in the Humanities Commons Terms of Service (<https://hcommons.org/terms/>). Items deposited in CORE fall under these terms (<https://hcommons.org/core/faq/>).

3.3.4 More help on Humanities Commons CORE

<https://support.hcommons.org/guides/>

4 How to Save to Zenodo

Uploading grey literature to Zenodo has three stages:

- Stage 1 – Get a DOI from Zenodo
- Stage 2 – Add the DOI and metadata into the grey literature
- Stage 3 – Upload the grey literature to Zenodo

4.1 Before you start

Important: Pause and get your metadata ready, as you will need it to create a DOI

You will need to have the following information ready about your grey literature before adding it to Zenodo:

- Title
- Authors/contributors and their ORCIDs (if you don't have an ORCID, sign up at <https://orcid.org/>)
- Funder (if applicable)
- Description
- Keywords – what this grey literature is about
- Choose a Creative Commons licence
 - More about CC licences - <https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/>
 - Help on choosing a CC licence - <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
 - See [sections 4.3.1](#) and [4.3.2](#) in this guide for how to copy a CC licence icon and hyperlink

4.1.1 Examples of metadata

Look at the metadata for one of these two grey literature examples in Zenodo if you need ideas for metadata:

Example 1 - Educational material

Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

Screenshot 1 – Example of Title, Authors, Description and Funder

Screenshot 2 – Example of Keywords, Zenodo community and Licence

Example 2 - Report

Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660>

December 12, 2021 Report Open Access

Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity

Quigley, Niamh

The Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI) in collaboration with Curtin University Library undertook a project to provide better support for the creative practice research outputs (CPROs) of Faculty of Humanities researchers. The reason for this research is to identify ways to increase the visibility of CPROs at Curtin University, and document what information (metadata) is important to researchers when describing their CPROs. The Chief Investigator of this project was Dr Lucy Montgomery, Professor of Knowledge Innovation at Curtin University. This research project has approval from the Curtin University Human Research Ethics Office (HRE2021-0515).

This report contains the creative practice research outputs metadata used during interviews as a card sorting activity, and the findings from interviews related to metadata. Templates for the card sorting activity are included in Appendices A and B of this document.

The interview guide including the card sort activity is available on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774543>

The deidentified interview transcripts are available on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774508>

This research was funded by the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative.

Screenshot 3 – Example of Title, Authors, Description and Funder

Publication date:
December 12, 2021

DOI:
DOI [10.5281/zenodo.5774660](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660)

Keyword(s):
[creative practice research outputs](#) [metadata](#)
[card sorting activity](#)

Communities:
[Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative](#)

License (for files):
[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#)

Screenshot 4 – Example of Keywords, Community and Licence

4.2 Stage 1 – Get a DOI from Zenodo

In Stage 1, you will enter metadata about your grey literature in Zenodo and get a DOI. When you upload to Zenodo, it creates two DOIs – a Version DOI and a Concept DOI:

- The Version DOI – a unique DOI for each version of your grey literature. Share this DOI with others if you want them to read a specific version. Zenodo uses the Version DOI to generate citations.
- The Concept DOI – a unique DOI that represents all of your versions (like a parent DOI). Share this DOI with others if you want them to read the latest version of your grey literature.²⁸

See the Zenodo Help guide for more information about DOI versions – <https://help.zenodo.org/> (scroll down to the DOI Versioning section).

4.2.1 Sign into Zenodo

Log into Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>, or create a new account if you don't have one at <https://zenodo.org/signup/>

Tip: Create your Zenodo account with an email address other than your university/work email, then you will have access to your Zenodo account if you change employer

4.2.2 Create new upload

Click Upload at the top and then New Upload on the right

Screenshot 5 – Upload screen in Zenodo

²⁸ <https://help.zenodo.org/>

The New upload screen will appear. Scroll down through the sections to enter information about your grey literature, with help from this guide.

Screenshot 6 – New upload screen in Zenodo

4.2.3 Communities section

Adding a community for your grey literature in Zenodo is optional (see screenshot 7). See [section 3.1.3](#) in this guide for more about how Zenodo communities can be used.

Screenshot 7 – Communities section in Zenodo

4.2.4 Upload type

In the *Upload type* section select **Publication**, and a **Publication type** if prompted (note that not all Publications have additional **Publication types** as in screenshot 8).

There are many **Upload types** suitable for grey literature in Zenodo:

Your grey literature	Zenodo Upload type	Zenodo Publication type
report	Publication	Report
working paper	Publication	Working paper
proposal	Publication	Proposal
position paper	Publication	Other
white paper	Publication	Other
some other type of document	Publication	Other
posters	Poster	N/A
infographic	Poster	N/A
videos	Video/Audio	N/A
podcasts	Video/Audio	N/A
interview recordings	Video/Audio	N/A
something else	Other	N/A

The screenshot shows the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, the 'Upload type' section is active, with a 'required' label and a dropdown arrow. Below this, there are ten radio buttons for different upload types: Publication (selected), Poster, Presentation, Dataset, Image, Video/Audio, Software, Lesson, Physical object, and Other. Under the 'Publication' radio button, there is a dropdown menu for 'Publication type' with 'Report' selected. Below the 'Publication type' dropdown, there is a 'Basic information' section, also marked as 'required'. It contains a text input field for 'Digital Object Identifier' with the placeholder 'e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar' and a 'Reserve DOI' button. A small note below the input field explains that a DOI is optional and provides instructions on how to use it.

Screenshot 8 – Upload type section in Zenodo

4.2.5 Basic Information section

4.2.5.1 Reserve DOI

In the *Basic Information* section, click on **Reserve DOI**.

The screenshot shows the 'Basic information' section in Zenodo. The 'Digital Object Identifier' field contains the placeholder text 'e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar'. Below the field is a 'Reserve DOI' button. The text below the field explains that a DOI is optional and will be registered if not provided, but it is not possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered.

Screenshot 9 – Basic information section in Zenodo before reserving a DOI

Zenodo will create a DOI and put it in the **Digital Object Identifier** field (see screenshot 10).

Important: Copy and save this DOI to somewhere on your computer as you will need it later in Stage 2 '[Add the DOI and metadata into the research output](#)'. The DOI that Zenodo generates will look something like this - '10.5281/zenodo.6122007'

The screenshot shows the 'Basic information' section in Zenodo. The 'Digital Object Identifier' field now contains the DOI '10.5281/zenodo.6122007'. The 'Reserve DOI' button is now disabled and has a green checkmark next to it, indicating that the DOI has been successfully reserved.

Screenshot 10 – Basic information section in Zenodo with reserved DOI

4.2.5.2 Complete Basic information

In the rest of the *Basic Information* section, fill out your grey literature details. For grey literature in the style of reports, consider copying the Description from your abstract or executive summary.

Sharing Research Beyond Academia: A Guide to Free Repositories for Researchers

Basic information required ▾

Digital Object Identifier
Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Reserve DOI

Publication date
Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Title
Required.

Authors

Optional.

Optional.

[+ Add another author](#)

Description

Screenshot 11 – Basic information section in Zenodo

Keywords can help more people find your grey literature e.g. audio description; Australia; position paper. Try to add at least 3 keywords.

Version
Optional. Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. Any string will be accepted, but semantically-versioned tag is recommended. See semver.org for more information on semantic versioning.

Language
Optional. Primary language of the record. Start by typing the language's common name in English, or its ISO 639 code (two or three-letter code). See [ISO 639 language codes list](https://iso639.org) for more information.

Keywords

[+ Add another keyword](#)

Additional notes
Optional.

Screenshot 12 – Basic information section in Zenodo

4.2.6 Licence

Make the grey literature as open as you can e.g. CC BY 4.0

- More about CC licences - <https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/>
- Help on choosing a CC licence - <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>

Screenshot 13 – License section in Zenodo

4.2.7 Funding/Additional notes

If the research leading to the grey literature was Australian Research Council (ARC) funded, you can add the funder & grant number in the *Funding* section

Screenshot 14 – Funding section in Zenodo

If the funder was not ARC and is not in the **Grants** dropdown, then add the funder to the **Additional Notes** field in the *Basic information* section.

Screenshot 15 – Additional notes section in Zenodo

4.2.8 Related/alternate identifiers

The *Related/alternate identifiers* section is optional. It can be used if you want to add a related publication or dataset, for example a journal article related to your grey literature. In the example below, the report being uploaded references a journal article about the same research.

Related/alternate identifiers recommended ▾

Specify identifiers of related publications and datasets. Supported identifiers include: DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, IOSTC, URNs and URLs.

Related identifiers ✕

Optional. Resource type of the related identifier.

[+ Add another related identifier](#)

Screenshot 16 – Related/alternate identifiers section in Zenodo

4.2.9 Contributors

The *Contributors* section is optional. It can be used to include people or groups that had a role in the research output, but are not authors. If this is useful for your grey literature, include their name, affiliation, ORCID and contribution type from the dropdown list.

Contributors optional ▾

Contributors ✕

Optional.

[+ Add another contributor](#)

Screenshot 17 – Contributors section in Zenodo

- Contact person
- Data collector
- Data curator
- Data manager
- Distributor
- Editor**
- Hosting institution
- Other
- Producer
- Project leader
- Project manager
- Project member
- Registration agency
- Registration authority
- Related person
- Research group
- Researcher
- Rights holder
- Sponsor
- Supervisor

Screenshot 18 – Contributors dropdown in Zenodo

4.2.10 Save the Zenodo record (not publish)

If you have filled in all the mandatory fields (the ones with a red star * in Zenodo), then select **Save**. Zenodo will let you know if you have missed any required fields.

A screenshot of the Zenodo interface showing the 'Subjects' section. At the top, there is a link '+ Add another supervisor'. Below that, the 'Subjects' section is titled 'Subjects' with a dropdown menu set to 'optional'. A descriptive text reads: 'Specify subjects from a taxonomy or controlled vocabulary. Each term must be uniquely identified (e.g. a URL). For free form text, use the keywords field in basic information section.' There is a table with two columns: 'Subjects' and 'Identifier'. The 'Subjects' column has a 'Term' input field, and the 'Identifier' column has an 'Identifier' input field. Below the table is a link '+ Add another subject'. At the bottom of the section, there are three buttons: a red 'Delete' button, a grey 'Save' button, and a blue 'Publish' button. The 'Save' button is circled in red.

Screenshot 19 – Saving a record in Zenodo

A message will appear to let you know that the record was saved.

Screenshot 20 – Successfully saved record in Zenodo

4.3 Stage 2 – Add the DOI and metadata into the research output

Now that a record has been created in Zenodo, and a DOI obtained in [section 4.2.5.1](#), Stage 2 is to add metadata into the research output (for example into a report). The final stage 3 will be to upload or publish the grey literature.

- Find the DOI that Zenodo gave you e.g. 10.5281/zenodo.6330620
- Add 'https://doi.org/' before this so it looks something like:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6330620>
- This is your DOI

4.3.1 Get a Creative Commons licence icon

You already chose a CC licence for your research output in section 4.1. You will need a CC licence icon to add into your research output. To download the icon for your chosen CC licence:

- Go to <https://creativecommons.org/about/downloads/>
- Scroll down to the 'Buttons' section
- Click on 'png' beside the CC licence you want to use, a large icon will open in a new tab
- Right-click on the CC licence icon, and select 'Copy image'
- Paste the CC licence icon image into your research output, and resize if needed.

4.3.2 Get a Creative Commons licence hyperlink

You already chose a CC licence for your research output in [section 4.1](#) of this guide. You will also need a CC licence hyperlink (URL) to add into your research output. You can get the hyperlink for your chosen CC licence using two ways:

- Choose your licence in the CC Licence Chooser
<https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
- Scroll to the 'Have a web page?' box
- Copy the CC licence text and hyperlink e.g. 'This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#)'
- Paste this text into your grey literature.
- **OR**
- Go to <https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/>
- Scroll down to the CC licence you have chosen
- Right click on the CC licence icon, and select 'Copy link address'
- This will copy the hyperlink e.g. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- In your research output, type the name of the CC licence e.g. 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License' and turn this into a link using the copied hyperlink.

4.3.3 Metadata template

You can add the following text to the first few pages of your research output, after the title page.

<paste Creative Commons licence icon>

© <Author1Name>, <Author3Name> and <Author3Name>. This guide is licensed under a <select Creative Commons licence and make it a hyperlink>.

Contributor statements:

<Author1Name>: Writing – original draft; <Author2Name>: Writing – review & editing; <Author3Name>: Writing – review & editing

Suggested citation:

<Author1Name>, <Author3Name> and <Author3Name>. (2022). Grey literature title. <Name of research group>. <DOI>

This research was funded by <funder>.

Contact: <contact email for research group/researcher>

4.3.4 Metadata example

Use this example as an idea of what your metadata should look like. This example included other peoples' creative work, so the text 'Except for third party works' was added.

© Niamh Quigley, Lucy Montgomery and Cameron Neylon. Except for third party works, this guide is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Contributor statements:

Niamh Quigley: Writing – original draft; Lucy Montgomery: Writing – review & editing; Cameron Neylon: Writing – review & editing

Suggested citation:

Quigley, N., Montgomery, L., Neylon, C. (2022). *Creative practice research outputs: Opportunities for Curtin University*. Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5935316>

This research was funded by the [Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative](#).

Contact: coki@curtin.edu.au

4.3.5 Metadata checklist

Check that you have included the following information about your research output (metadata):

- A unique identifier such as a DOI
- Title
- Authors, contributors and reviewers, and any acknowledgements
- Version
- Research group
- Date published
- How the grey literature can be reused – copyright/Creative Commons
- Suggested citation
- Funder
- Contact email (can be an individual or a group)

4.3.6 Which format to publish – Word document or PDF

Zenodo supports both .docx and PDF file formats. The advantages of using a PDF is that it will be readable from within Zenodo in their PDF viewer, and the formatting will appear the same for everyone.

4.4 Stage 3 – Upload to Zenodo

Now that you have added the DOI and metadata to your research output, you can upload it to Zenodo.

If you are still logged into Zenodo, where you saved a record in Stage 2, scroll to the *Files* section at the top. You can check you're in the right record by looking at the DOI and Title.

(If you aren't logged into Zenodo, log in at <https://zenodo.org/> and click on Upload at the top. Select the research output that you were using in Stage 2.)

In the *Files* section at the top, click on **Choose files** (see screenshot 21). Select the research output file on your computer that you want to upload, for the DOI and metadata entered in Stage 2.

New upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press "Save" to save your upload for e

Files ▾

Drag and drop files here

— or —

Choose files

(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us)
If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ

Communities ⓘ

Specify communities which you wish your upload to appear in. The owner of the community will be notified, and your upload must comply with the content policy of the communities you add; reported abuse will be followed by account inactivation.

Start typing a community name...

Upload type

Publication Poster Presentation Dataset Image Video/Audio

Publication type Project deliverable
Publication type.

Basic information

Digital Object Identifier 10.5281/zenodo.6330620
Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If n

Screenshot 21 – Choosing a file to upload in Zenodo

After you've selected the file on your computer to upload, Zenodo will look like screenshot 22. Click on the green button **Start upload**.

Screenshot 22 – Start upload for a file in Zenodo

After the Upload is complete, there will be a green tick under **Progress**. Click on **Publish**.

Screenshot 23 – Completed upload for a file in Zenodo

The following Warning message is expected, and is just checking that you really want to upload a file. Click on **I understand**.

Screenshot 24 – Expected warning message when uploading a file in Zenodo

You should now see a screen that looks something like Screenshot 25. Note that only you can see the **Edit** button, because you are logged in and looking at your own Zenodo files.

Screenshot 25 – Published record in Zenodo (view when logged in)

Everyone else will see something like screenshot 26:

The screenshot shows a Zenodo dataset record. At the top left, the date 'February 17, 2022' is displayed. To the right are two buttons: 'Dataset' and 'Open Access'. The main title is 'HRE2021-0515-03 Research Data: Focus Group Transcripts'. Below the title is the author's name 'Quigley, Niamh' with an ORCID icon. The description states: 'The Centre for Culture and Technology (CCAT) undertook a project aiming to provide better support for grey literature research outputs including reports, working papers and blog posts. The research team for the project 'Increasing the Visibility of Grey Literature' was:'. A bulleted list follows: 'Professor Katie Ellis, Centre for Culture and Technology' and 'Niamh Quigley, Research Associate, Centre for Culture and Technology'. Below this, it says 'This dataset contains the deidentified transcripts of two focus groups held with producers of grey literature at Curtin University Perth, Australia. The'. On the right side, there are three summary boxes. The top one shows '0 views' and '0 downloads' with a link to 'See more details...'. The middle one says 'Indexed in' with the 'OpenAIRE' logo. The bottom one shows 'Publication date: February 17, 2022' and 'DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6122007'.

Screenshot 26 – Published record in Zenodo (view for others)

Your research output is now online, and available to view and download.

In the future, you can use the **Edit** button (see screenshot 25) if you need to change any of the information (metadata) about your research output. If you need to upload a new file, for example a new version of a position paper, use the **New version** button. When you upload a new version of your file, Zenodo will give you a new DOI specific to that version. To learn more about Zenodo's DOI versioning system, see [section 4.2 Stage 1 – Get a DOI from Zenodo](#) in this guide.

5 Adding Research Outputs to ORCID

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a free unique, persistent identifier for researchers.²⁹ Increasingly funders and journals are asking researchers to provide their ORCID, as it makes it easier to link researchers with their research outputs.

If you don't already have an ORCID, sign up for one at <https://orcid.org/>

This section presents three ways to get your research outputs into your ORCID publication record:

- Adding a research output that has a DOI (using an example of a report)
- Adding a research output that does not have a DOI (using an example of a zine article)
- Setting up ORCID auto-update between Zenodo (via DataCite) and ORCID

Log into ORCID

1. Log into ORCID <https://orcid.org/>
2. Scroll down to the Works part of your ORCID profile and click on **Add** on the right-hand side:

Screenshot 27 – Adding a work to ORCID

3. There are two ways to link your grey literature to ORCID:
 - Option 1 – add a research output that has a DOI (go to [section 5.1](#))
 - Option 2 – add a research output that does not have a DOI (go to [section 5.2](#))
 - Option 3 – for research outputs that you have added to Zenodo, you can set up ORCID to auto-update between Zenodo (via DataCite) and ORCID (go to [section 5.3](#))

²⁹ <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

5.1 Option 1 – Add a research output that has a DOI

In this example, a report in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5935316>) will be added to the Works section in ORCID. Log into ORCID.

1. To add one research output at a time, click on 'Add DOI' in the Add menu

Screenshot 28 – Add menu -> Add DOI

2. Copy your DOI from Zenodo and add it to the 'DOI identifier value or full URL' field.

Screenshot 29 – Works - Add a DOI

3. Click on 'Retrieve work details from DOI'. ORCID will read as much as it can about the work from Zenodo, and will display a Works popup:

Screenshot 30 – Add work from DOI popup

4. Scroll down to check everything is correct, and make sure all mandatory fields with a red * are filled in. Fill in any other fields required, for example add a 'Country of publication':

Screenshot 31 – Add work from DOI popup (Other information section)

5. Click on 'Add this work to your ORCID record'. The work will now be displayed in the Works section of your ORCID record. Note that the Works section defaults to show the newest publications first, so the work you have just added might not be at the top. Click on 'Show more detail' for any work, to show more information about it.

Screenshot 32 – ORCID record – Works section

Screenshot 33 – ORCID record – Works section – More detail for a work

6. If anything needs to be changed, click on edit (pen icon) to update this work.
7. Tip - If you find multiple versions of the same work in your ORCID record, you can delete the unwanted version by clicking on the delete (bin icon). The Source section in the details of a work shows where the information about the work came from.

5.2 Option 2 – Add a research output that does not have a DOI

In this example, a zine article with no DOI (<http://violetbfox.info/disorientation/>) will be added to the Works section in ORCID. Log into ORCID.

1. To add a research output that does not have a DOI to your ORCID record, click on 'Add manually' in the Add menu.

Screenshot 34 – Add menu → Add manually

2. The 'Works' popup will be displayed with all fields blank.

A screenshot of the ORCID 'Works' popup form. The form is titled 'Works' and has a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form is divided into sections: 'Work details', 'Citation', and 'Visibility'. The 'Work details' section includes fields for 'Work type*' (a dropdown menu), 'Title*' (a text input field), 'Add translated title' (a button), 'Work Subtitle' (a text input field), 'Journal title' (a text input field), 'Publication date' (three dropdown menus for Year, Month, and Day), and 'Link' (a text input field). The 'Citation' section has a 'Save changes' button and a 'Cancel' button. The 'Visibility' section is currently empty. A note at the bottom of the form states: 'A link to more information about the work. Links should be in the full URL format e.g. http://www.website.com/page.html'.

Screenshot 35 – Add work popup (blank)

3. Fill in all mandatory fields with a red *, and as many optional fields as you can.
- Work Type – select from the dropdown. Some suitable work types are: magazine article; newsletter article; newspaper article; online resource; report; and working paper.
Choose 'Other' if you can't find a suitable work type
 - Title
 - Link – include the online location of your grey literature output
 - Citation – add a citation
 - Description – this field is not mandatory, but can be used to add extra information.

The screenshot shows a 'Works' popup window with a dark header and a close button. The main content area is titled 'Work details' and includes a red asterisk indicating required information. The form is filled with the following data:

- Work type***: Magazine article
- Title***: Library Systems are Not Perfect: Describing Transgende
- Add translated title**: + (button)
- Work Subtitle**: (empty)
- Magazine title**: Disorientation Guide to Librarianship
- Publication date**: 2021, 10, Day
- Link**: <http://violetbox.info/disorientation/>
- Citation type**: APA
- Citation**: Quigley, N. (2021, October). Library systems are not perfect: Describing transgender children and young people using LCSH. Disorientation Guide to Librarianship. <http://violetbox.info/disorientation/>
- Description**: Editor: Violet B. Fox
Disorientation Guide to Librarianship is a compilation zine created by 23 contributors and published in October 2021. The zine is designed to be an accessible resource for people who are unfamiliar with structural oppression and injustice in librarianship. It is intended

At the bottom, there are 'Save changes' and 'Cancel' buttons. A vertical sidebar on the right contains navigation links: Work details, Identifiers, Citation, Other information, and Visibility.

Screenshot 36 – Add work popup (filled in)

4. Click on 'Save changes' to add the work to your ORCID record. The work will now be displayed in the Works section of your ORCID record. Note that the Works section defaults to show the newest publications first, so the work you have just added might not be at the top. Click on 'Show more detail' for any work, to show more information about it.

Screenshot 37 - ORCID record – Works section – More detail for a work

5. If anything needs to be changed, click on edit (pen icon) to update this work.
6. Tip - If you find multiple versions of the same work in your ORCID record, you can delete the unwanted version by clicking on the delete (bin icon). The Source section in the details of a work shows where the information about the work came from.

5.3 Option 3 – Set up ORCID to auto-update between Zenodo and ORCID

You can also enable ORCID to auto-update, so that every time you upload to Zenodo your ORCID publication record automatically updates. To enable ORCID auto-update, follow these instructions from DataCite: <https://support.datacite.org/docs/how-to-activate-orcid-auto-update>.

You will first be prompted to sign into DataCite Profiles on Globus, using your ORCID account details. This will authorise access for DataCite to your ORCID record. Once you're logged into your DataCite Profile, follow these instructions from DataCite on how to auto-enable ORCID in the DataCite Profile Settings:

<https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-profiles-user-documentation>.

If your Zenodo publications are still not appearing in your ORCID publication record, you can add them manually (see [section 5.1 Option 1 – Add a research output that has a DOI](#) in this guide).

6 Sharing Your Research Outputs Beyond Academia

Tip: When you're sharing your research outputs with others, use the DOI rather than the URL. For example in Zenodo:

✓ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660>

× <https://zenodo.org/record/5774660>

6.1 Alternative metrics

Alternative metrics measure online attention by tracking who has engaged with your research outputs and grey literature across different platforms. You can read more about alternative metrics here:

<https://libguides.library.curtin.edu.au/c.php?g=889921&p=6401380>

Research outputs that have DOIs are eligible for Altmetrics. This means you can see who is engaging with your grey literature online. Especially for Twitter, this can give you an insight into who is reading your grey literature, and an opportunity to engage with them.

There are two ways to use Altmetric:

Altmetric Bookmarklet

- Free bookmarklet for Chrome, Firefox and Safari
- Free to all but must use Curtin email address
- Download instructions here - <https://www.altmetric.com/products/free-tools/bookmarklet/>

Institutional Altmetric

- Free if you use your Curtin email address (Curtin University have a paid subscription) [more info here](#)
- Sign up here <https://www.altmetric.com/explorer/login>
- More features than the Altmetrics Bookmarklet

6.2 APO (Analysis & Policy Observatory)

To increase the visibility of grey literature such as reports, consider submitting it to APO <https://apo.org.au/how-to-use>. There are options to upload a copy of the grey literature or provide a link to the repository where a copy of the grey literature is already available online. Learn more about the APO here <https://apo.org.au/page/about-apo>.

6.3 Professional associations

Many professional associations share recommendations for professional development resources with their members. Open access grey literature is especially relevant as it is free to access for all. Consider sending your report, blog post or education material to a relevant professional association.

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